

MASCOT SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

User :
 Email :
 Search title :
 MS data file : C:\Documents and Settings\Proteomics\Desktop\3736\151127_3736C.wiff.mgf
 Database : MSPnr100_Q315 (75925788 sequences; 27045014025 residues)
 Taxonomy : Rattus (95208 sequences)
 Timestamp : 1 Dec 2015 at 05:02:07 GMT
 Protein hits : [D4A9T1](#) tr|D4A9T1|Rnf111 D4A9T1_RAT Protein Rnf111 n=7 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]

Mascot Score Histogram

Ions score is $-10 \cdot \log(P)$, where P is the probability that the observed match is a random event. Individual ions scores > 36 indicate identity or extensive homology ($p < 0.05$). Protein scores are derived from ions scores as a non-probabilistic basis for ranking protein hits.

Peptide Summary Report

Format As [Help](#)

Significance threshold $p < 0.05$ Max. number of hits

Standard scoring MudPIT scoring Ions score or expect cut-off Show sub-sets

Show pop-ups Suppress pop-ups Sort unassigned Require bold red

Preferred taxonomy

Error tolerant

1. [D4A9T1](#) Mass: 107513 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1) emPAI: 0.03
 tr|D4A9T1|Rnf111 D4A9T1_RAT Protein Rnf111 n=7 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	Delta	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
☒ 72	513.7973	1025.5801	1025.6233	-0.0432	0	36	0.05	1	U	R.ISTVIQPLR.Q
☒ 73	513.7990	1025.5835	1025.6233	-0.0398	0	(30)	0.24	1	U	R.ISTVIQPLR.Q
☒ 74	513.8007	1025.5868	1025.6233	-0.0366	0	(26)	0.58	1	U	R.ISTVIQPLR.Q
☒ 75	513.8012	1025.5878	1025.6233	-0.0355	0	(25)	0.73	1	U	R.ISTVIQPLR.Q
☒ 76	513.8017	1025.5888	1025.6233	-0.0345	0	(23)	1.1	1	U	R.ISTVIQPLR.Q

Proteins matching the same set of peptides:

[ENSRNOP0000069573](#) Mass: 106549 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 ens|ENSRNOP0000069573|ENSRNOG0000060750 transcript:ENSRNOT0000082709 gene_biotype:protein_coding transcript_biotype:protein_coding n=1 Tax_I
[XP_006243434.1](#) Mass: 117927 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 ref|XP_006243434.1| PREDICTED: E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase Arkadia isoform X2 n=2 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]
[XP_006243435.1](#) Mass: 116962 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 ref|XP_006243435.1| PREDICTED: E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase Arkadia isoform X4 n=2 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]
[XP_006243436.1](#) Mass: 116834 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 ref|XP_006243436.1| PREDICTED: E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase Arkadia isoform X5 n=2 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]
[XP_008764465.1](#) Mass: 117799 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 ref|XP_008764465.1| PREDICTED: E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase Arkadia isoform X3 n=2 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]
[XP_008764467.1](#) Mass: 117971 Score: 36 Matches: 5(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 ref|XP_008764467.1| PREDICTED: E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase Arkadia isoform X6 n=2 Tax_Id=10116 [Rattus norvegicus]

Peptide matches not assigned to protein hits: (no details means no match)

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	Delta	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
☒ 7	598.3572	597.3499	597.4214	-0.0714	1	24	0.48	1		KIPIK
☒ 109	577.2912	1152.5679	1152.5485	0.0194	0	22	1.5	1		SSPMVQVDYK
☒ 104	577.2908	1152.5671	1152.6000	-0.0329	0	22	1.6	1		IVQSHQQTGR
☒ 47	501.2854	1000.5563	1000.5917	-0.0354	0	21	2.3	1		TTQVALGLAK
☒ 155	675.3421	1348.6697	1348.5791	0.0906	0	20	1.9	1		SYFMECLVDAR + Oxidation (M)
☒ 127	587.3262	1172.6379	1172.6149	0.0230	0	20	2.4	1		SEQAIGATAASR
☒ 131	589.2699	1176.5252	1176.5995	-0.0743	0	20	2.2	1		MNMGVAVAVLK
☒ 124	587.3250	1172.6355	1172.7030	-0.0674	1	20	2.5	1		FGQSKPILRK
☒ 129	587.3282	1172.6419	1172.6149	0.0269	0	20	2.5	1		SEQAIGATAASR
☒ 130	587.3283	1172.6420	1172.6149	0.0270	0	19	2.7	1		SEQAIGATAASR
☒ 110	577.2913	1152.5680	1152.6000	-0.0319	0	19	2.6	1		IVQSHQQTGR
☒ 117	577.2938	1152.5731	1152.6000	-0.0269	0	19	2.7	1		IVQSHQQTGR

✓	128	587.3272	1172.6398	1172.6037	0.0362	1	19	3	1	EKLSEPGQASK
✓	162	675.3454	1348.6763	1348.5791	0.0971	0	19	2.6	1	SYFMECLVDAR + Oxidation (M)
✓	111	577.2913	1152.5680	1152.6000	-0.0319	0	19	2.9	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	114	577.2919	1152.5693	1152.6000	-0.0307	0	19	3	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	45	501.2837	1000.5529	1000.5917	-0.0388	1	19	3.6	1	LAKADGIVSK
✓	102	577.2898	1152.5651	1152.6000	-0.0349	0	18	3.1	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	118	577.2945	1152.5745	1152.5272	0.0473	0	18	3.3	1	SSHSDTHVQR
✓	126	587.3261	1172.6376	1172.6149	0.0227	0	18	3.5	1	SEQAIGATAASR
✓	105	577.2908	1152.5671	1152.6000	-0.0329	0	18	3.5	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	98	577.2850	1152.5555	1152.6000	-0.0445	0	18	3.5	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	100	577.2886	1152.5626	1152.5272	0.0354	0	18	3.7	1	SSHSDTHVQR
✓	135	598.2908	1194.5671	1194.6318	-0.0648	0	18	3.3	1	ACLSLFVSDLK
✓	112	577.2913	1152.5680	1152.6000	-0.0319	0	18	3.7	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	108	577.2912	1152.5679	1152.5710	-0.0031	1	18	3.9	1	ARSAGGAFCSVK
✓	125	587.3255	1172.6365	1172.6149	0.0216	0	17	4.4	1	SEQAIGATAASR
✓	106	577.2908	1152.5671	1152.6000	-0.0329	0	17	4.1	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	67	509.2739	1016.5332	1016.6052	-0.0720	1	17	5.1	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	57	509.2705	1016.5264	1016.6052	-0.0788	1	17	5.1	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	60	509.2721	1016.5296	1016.6052	-0.0756	1	17	5.2	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	58	509.2712	1016.5279	1016.6052	-0.0773	1	17	5.3	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	63	509.2725	1016.5305	1016.6052	-0.0748	1	17	5.5	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	61	509.2721	1016.5296	1016.6052	-0.0756	1	17	5.5	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	66	509.2734	1016.5323	1016.6052	-0.0729	1	17	5.5	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	59	509.2720	1016.5294	1016.6052	-0.0758	1	17	5.7	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	101	577.2898	1152.5651	1152.6000	-0.0349	0	17	5	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	107	577.2910	1152.5674	1152.5272	0.0402	0	16	5.1	1	SSHSDTHVQR
✓	68	509.2755	1016.5365	1016.6052	-0.0688	1	16	6.1	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	146	425.2283	1272.6632	1272.5842	0.0789	1	16	5.7	1	MTKFIDDTMR + Oxidation (M)
✓	119	577.2971	1152.5796	1152.6000	-0.0204	0	16	5.9	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	99	577.2882	1152.5618	1152.6000	-0.0382	0	16	6.1	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	134	596.2661	1190.5176	1190.6143	-0.0967	0	16	6	1	QIASSPSSSLK
✓	120	577.2992	1152.5838	1152.5710	0.0128	1	15	6.3	1	ARSAGGAFCSVK
✓	115	577.2921	1152.5696	1152.5485	0.0211	0	15	6.6	1	SSPMVQVDYK
✓	136	598.2963	1194.5780	1194.6244	-0.0465	0	15	6	1	DTIYNTILSR
✓	158	675.3434	1348.6723	1348.5791	0.0931	0	15	6.3	1	SYFMECLVDAR + Oxidation (M)
✓	151	653.3245	1304.6345	1304.7241	-0.0896	1	15	6.5	1	QKAIIDLLYWR
✓	161	675.3444	1348.6743	1348.5791	0.0952	0	15	6.3	1	SYFMECLVDAR + Oxidation (M)
✓	145	425.2280	1272.6620	1272.5842	0.0778	1	15	7.5	1	MTKFIDDTMR + Oxidation (M)
✓	65	509.2733	1016.5320	1016.6052	-0.0732	1	15	8.4	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	62	509.2723	1016.5300	1016.6052	-0.0752	1	15	8.4	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	64	509.2727	1016.5309	1016.6052	-0.0743	1	15	8.5	1	VKLMVNLGK + Oxidation (M)
✓	156	675.3427	1348.6709	1348.6293	0.0416	0	15	7	1	DVNLASCAADGSVK
✓	53	501.7941	1001.5736	1001.5029	0.0707	0	15	9.8	1	QLGSPTDLA
✓	157	675.3431	1348.6716	1348.6293	0.0423	0	14	7.4	1	DVNLASCAADGSVK
✓	159	675.3440	1348.6734	1348.6293	0.0441	0	14	7.7	1	DVNLASCAADGSVK
✓	137	598.2976	1194.5807	1194.6318	-0.0511	0	14	7.8	1	ACLSLFVSDLK
✓	160	675.3440	1348.6734	1348.5791	0.0943	0	14	8.6	1	SYFMECLVDAR + Oxidation (M)
✓	144	633.8233	1265.6321	1265.6299	0.0022	1	14	8.4	1	ARPFERSTMR + Oxidation (M)
✓	103	577.2905	1152.5665	1152.5485	0.0180	0	14	9.8	1	SSPMVQVDYK
✓	79	520.8069	1039.5993	1039.5774	0.0219	1	13	9.6	1	KAAGSGSPPLR
✓	43	501.2822	1000.5499	1000.5301	0.0197	0	13	14	1	IASLDAANAR
✓	148	638.8343	1275.6541	1275.6571	-0.0031	1	13	12	1	DISQNFPTKAR
✓	133	596.2644	1190.5142	1190.6143	-0.1001	0	12	13	1	QIASSPSSSLK
✓	44	501.2832	1000.5518	1000.5189	0.0329	0	12	17	1	SPSTLQSPGK
✓	147	638.8325	1275.6505	1275.5410	0.1095	1	12	15	1	GCKMNVNGAPCPP + Oxidation (M)
✓	153	653.3271	1304.6396	1304.7677	-0.1281	1	12	14	1	AKGALAHAVQALR
✓	82	520.8098	1039.6050	1039.5774	0.0276	1	11	15	1	KAAGSGSPPLR
✓	80	520.8081	1039.6017	1039.5774	0.0243	1	11	16	1	KAAGSGSPPLR
✓	152	653.3258	1304.6370	1304.7241	-0.0870	1	11	17	1	QKAIIDLLYWR
✓	42	501.2766	1000.5387	1000.5301	0.0086	0	11	23	1	IASLDAANAR
✓	49	501.2992	1000.5838	1000.5189	0.0649	0	10	30	1	SPSTLQSPGK
✓	54	501.7956	1001.5766	1001.5029	0.0737	0	9	32	1	QLGSPTDLA
✓	116	577.2927	1152.5708	1152.5748	-0.0041	1	9	25	1	NPTSHRAGTGR
✓	81	520.8096	1039.6046	1039.5774	0.0272	1	9	25	1	KAAGSGSPPLR
✓	113	577.2914	1152.5682	1152.6000	-0.0318	0	9	31	1	IVQSHQQTGR
✓	46	501.2845	1000.5545	1000.4648	0.0898	0	8	42	1	MASPPDLR
✓	20	452.2608	902.5071	902.4320	0.0751	0	8	54	1	YGGPMPGPK
✓	14	436.2397	870.4648	870.5175	-0.0527	0	8	43	1	VTVTVPQK
✓	32	480.2737	958.5328	958.4719	0.0609	1	7	53	1	NKSPDAEAK
✓	84	524.2853	1046.5561	1046.5217	0.0344	1	7	51	1	TSNSGRQAAR
✓	179	1082.0377	2162.0608	2162.1154	-0.0546	0	7	25	1	NDMTEPHKPLTQLLPGISR + Oxidation (M)
✓	21	458.2643	914.5141	914.5437	-0.0295	1	6	64	1	VEVLEAKK
✓	52	501.7935	1001.5725	1001.5328	0.0397	0	6	66	1	CTPLSTRPK
✓	38	494.2828	986.5511	986.5509	0.0002	1	6	62	1	GLRNAISEK
✓	8	414.2473	826.4800	826.4661	0.0139	0	6	57	1	LPSVQQR
✓	36	489.3108	976.6071	976.5375	0.0696	1	5	81	1	MLRTLEAK + Oxidation (M)
✓	139	604.3472	1206.6798	1206.6145	0.0652	1	5	71	1	FGEVGSARWK
✓	178	1082.0372	2162.0599	2162.1154	-0.0555	0	5	39	1	NDMTEPHKPLTQLLPGISR + Oxidation (M)
✓	41	501.2498	1000.4851	1000.5917	-0.1066	1	5	90	1	LAKADGIVSK
✓	121	577.3659	1152.7172	1152.5817	0.1355	1	5	67	1	LICKLSMSCR
✓	37	489.3135	976.6125	976.5375	0.0750	1	5	98	1	MLRTLEAK + Oxidation (M)
✓	51	501.7926	1001.5705	1001.5029	0.0676	0	4	1e+02	1	QLGSPTDLA

☒	29	479.2759	956.5372	956.4675	0.0696	1	4	96	1	RAPGDQGEK
☒	71	511.3225	1020.6305	1020.4546	0.1759	0	4	88	1	MALGGEGQDK + Oxidation (M)
☒	170	753.4674	1504.9202	1504.7885	0.1317	1	4	47	1	GKSPAQAELSYLNK
☒	95	562.3605	1122.7064	1122.6437	0.0626	1	4	77	1	YGIKFPTIK
☒	50	501.7921	1001.5696	1001.5029	0.0666	0	4	1.1e+02	1	QLGSPITDLA
☒	83	523.3129	1044.6112	1044.5087	0.1025	0	4	1.1e+02	1	EVNPAATTDK
☒	48	501.2958	1000.5771	1000.5198	0.0573	0	4	1.1e+02	1	LSMLGCHIK
☒	87	538.3211	1074.6277	1074.4877	0.1400	1	4	1.1e+02	1	CSRHVQTSGT
☒	55	502.2676	1002.5207	1002.4151	0.1056	0	4	1.1e+02	1	TTDMFPGGK + Oxidation (M)
☒	33	480.8003	959.5861	959.4059	0.1803	0	4	1.2e+02	1	ECTFFSLN
☒	27	472.2758	942.5371	942.5247	0.0125	0	4	1.1e+02	1	QNLVVTNR
☒	93	560.3240	1118.6335	1118.5906	0.0428	0	3	1.2e+02	1	APFLGMSQLR
☒	177	1082.0363	2162.0580	2162.0275	0.0305	0	3	56	1	ASIMFLQSLDSVVEFCTEK + Oxidation (M)
☒	78	518.3169	1034.6193	1034.5185	0.1008	0	3	1.2e+02	1	HSYFEKPK
☒	92	555.3491	1108.6836	1108.4972	0.1865	0	3	1.1e+02	1	THTMGGAFFSGK + Oxidation (M)
☒	69	509.8230	1017.6315	1017.5607	0.0708	1	2	1.5e+02	1	THTGLKSFK
☒	10	423.2512	844.4879	844.4403	0.0477	1	2	1.8e+02	1	NSPAGKSGK
☒	26	467.2989	932.5833	932.5113	0.0720	1	2	1.7e+02	1	ELQIMRK + Oxidation (M)
☒	23	465.7989	929.5832	929.4494	0.1337	0	2	1.6e+02	1	TYIFSGDK
☒	166	477.5829	1429.7268	1429.7790	-0.0522	1	2	1.2e+02	1	QHPPLQPRASATK
☒	35	489.2470	976.4794	976.4535	0.0258	1	2	1.9e+02	1	ELKATPGDM + Oxidation (M)
☒	167	477.5845	1429.7318	1429.7599	-0.0281	0	2	1.2e+02	1	GLLSPLMSRPESK + Oxidation (M)
☒	22	458.7885	915.5625	915.4596	0.1029	1	2	1.9e+02	1	LEKSMHR + Oxidation (M)
☒	70	510.2706	1018.5266	1018.5560	-0.0294	0	2	1.7e+02	1	GNLGGVSFR
☒	9	414.2482	826.4819	826.5388	-0.0570	1	2	1.5e+02	1	VLAAGLRK
☒	173	819.5134	1637.0123	1636.8681	0.1443	1	1	66	1	TYVGAMPKIIQCLK + Oxidation (M)
☒	24	467.2195	932.4244	932.4749	-0.0505	1	1	2.2e+02	1	TPNQMKAK + Oxidation (M)
☒	17	445.2454	888.4762	888.4301	0.0461	1	1	2.4e+02	1	SPRSEGEK
☒	86	533.3389	1064.6633	1064.4887	0.1746	0	1	1.8e+02	1	NQDGTIDFR
☒	13	436.2367	870.4589	870.3654	0.0936	1	0	2.2e+02	1	RDMDYR + Oxidation (M)
☒	94	562.3413	1122.6680	1122.5591	0.1089	0	0	2.1e+02	1	QTATILSMDK + Oxidation (M)
☒	77	516.3003	1030.5861	1030.4792	0.1069	1	0	2.7e+02	1	VNREGEGDR
☒	132	590.3204	1178.6262	1178.6196	0.0066	1	0	2e+02	1	SLAFFKDHKK
☒	1	406.2463	405.2391							
☒	2	446.2424	445.2352							
☒	3	450.2359	449.2286							
☒	4	518.2556	517.2483							
☒	5	520.2757	519.2684							
☒	6	524.2455	523.2383							
☒	11	423.2702	844.5258							
☒	12	435.2415	868.4685							
☒	15	436.7764	871.5382							
☒	16	436.7775	871.5405							
☒	18	445.2518	888.4890							
☒	19	450.2739	898.5333							
☒	25	467.2877	932.5608							
☒	28	474.2716	946.5286							
☒	30	479.2898	956.5651							
☒	31	480.2732	958.5318							
☒	34	487.8110	973.6075							
☒	39	496.3013	990.5880							
☒	40	496.3053	990.5961							
☒	56	502.8122	1003.6099							
☒	85	531.8388	1061.6630							
☒	88	540.3395	1078.6645							
☒	89	540.3408	1078.6670							
☒	90	545.3176	1088.6207							
☒	91	546.8378	1091.6611							
☒	96	568.3119	1134.6093							
☒	97	568.3127	1134.6108							
☒	122	584.3653	1166.7160							
☒	123	584.3752	1166.7359							
☒	138	599.3776	1196.7407							
☒	140	606.3849	1210.7552							
☒	141	606.3893	1210.7640							
☒	142	621.3938	1240.7730							
☒	143	628.3921	1254.7696							
☒	149	643.4048	1284.7950							
☒	150	643.4050	1284.7955							
☒	154	665.4224	1328.8303							
☒	163	687.4334	1372.8523							
☒	164	467.2195	1398.6367							
☒	165	709.4459	1416.8772							
☒	168	731.4566	1460.8986							
☒	169	489.2470	1464.7191							
☒	171	775.4849	1548.9553							
☒	172	797.4991	1592.9837							
☒	174	841.5227	1681.0308							
☒	175	467.2195	1864.8489							
☒	176	489.2470	1952.9587							

Search Parameters

Type of search : MS/MS Ion Search
Enzyme : Trypsin
Variable modifications : [Oxidation \(M\)](#)
Mass values : Monoisotopic
Protein Mass : Unrestricted
Peptide Mass Tolerance : ± 0.2 Da
Fragment Mass Tolerance : ± 0.2 Da
Max Missed Cleavages : 1
Instrument type : ESI-QUAD-TOF
Number of queries : 179

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>